

Deliverable D7.7

EU:s role in leading Global systems of human rights and democracy in: Multinational, regional or bilateral cooperation

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EU role leading Global system of human rights and democracy in: multinational, regional or bilateral cooperation, reflecting geopolitical issues

1 Executive Summary: The HRJust Project

The HRJust project is designed to investigate the emerging phenomenon of Human Rights Justifications (HRJs). Historically, human rights were conceptualised as a ‘normative shield’ possessed by individuals to protect them against the potentially overreaching power of the State. However, the project identifies a paradigm shift: States are increasingly utilising the

subject of human rights, activating rights language to defend and legitimise their own governance decisions and actions. This shift creates two primary regulatory gaps. First, there is no international, regional, or national regime that regulates how States use human rights to justify their actions. Second, the protection of individual human rights is often weakened when States appropriate rights language as a tool of governance rather than a mechanism of protection. HRJust aims to develop a robust theory of HRJs and implement a process for Systematic Ongoing Direct Civil Society Engagement. By focusing on five countries—Sweden, Finland, Taiwan, India, and Ukraine—and three thematic areas (Covid-19, Migration, and Climate), the project provides recommendations to the EU on promoting transnational democratic governance and mending these gaps in human rights protection.

2 Deliverable 7.7

According to the HRJust Grant Agreement, Deliverable 7.7 is a report on the EU's role in the Global system of human rights and democracy in regard to multinational, regional or bilateral cooperation, reflecting geopolitical issues. It is situated within Work Package 7 (Empirical-Cross-cutting) which brings together experts on gender, intersectionality, law, anthropology and sociology, with the Coordinator to oversee synthesis and produce a coherent set of findings and recommendations on cross cutting issues raised by Human Rights Justifications (HRJs).

The lead beneficiary of WP 7 originally was the University of Lapland (UoL) with joint responsibility between the Institute of International Relations (IIR) which was the lead beneficiary of Deliverable 7.7. However, UoL withdrew from the project in year 2, while IIR withdrew from the project in year 3. The University of Bern has also withdrawn from the project in year three. University of Helsinki (UoH) has assumed the main responsibility for this Work Package 7 deliverable 7.7 that has also been prepared by experts in EU law from Work Packages 4-6.

According to the HRJust Grant Agreement, Deliverable 7.7 is required to address the following standard set of four questions:

- (i) How do States defend and legitimise its actions through human rights?
- (ii) Compare the general and the particular.
- (iii) What role does geopolitics play in strategy, resources and reach.

- (iv) What role has EU in comparison between internal to EU and external to EU?

In addition, Deliverable 7.7 is to make policy recommendations for a global system of human rights and democracy for the EU in support of a multinational human rights system and promotion of transnational democratic governance.

Deliverable 7.7 is largely, if not exclusively, a synthesis report, merging a major part of the research work done within WP3 (Normative-Theory), WP4 (Covid), WP5 (Migration) and WP6 (Climate) and discussing their outcomes with a view to arriving at identification of policy recommendations for a global system for human rights and democracy and the implications for the internal and external roles of EU. In particular, Deliverable 7.7 is able to take advantage of the research results, including policy recommendations, presented in the following deliverables of HRJust research consortium:

1. Deliverable 2.2 – Recommendations on policy, legislation and regulations, EU role and addressing gaps in regulations and individual human rights protection as effects of States' HRJ;
2. Deliverable.3.2 – Typology and Evaluation of Human Rights Justifications;
3. Deliverable 7.5 – Inclusive Democracy, reflecting gender and intersectionality;
4. Deliverable 7.6 – Overview of States' practice of HRJs, including findings in three thematic WPs; and
5. The report, "A Normative Core for a Geopolitical Europe: Policy Recommendation on Human Rights in European Union External Action", by Sari Kouvo represent background research towards this deliverable 7.7.

3 Setting the scene

3.1 Fundamental and human rights in the EU and its external relations

According to the HRJust Grant Agreement, Deliverable 7.7 is set to address, among others, the question of what role the EU has in comparison between relations internal and external to the EU in the system of human rights and democracy. For this purpose, a brief overview of human rights in the EU and its external relations is needed.

Human rights¹ operate in the EU both internally and externally. On the one hand, there is the EU's internal system for the protection of fundamental rights which is nowadays largely codified in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (EUCFR), but which also still takes the form of unwritten general principles of EU law in which fundamental rights found their first mention in in the classic cases of *Stauder*, *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft* and *Nold* at the turn of the 1970s.²

Article 6 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU) is the central provision of fundamental rights protection in the EU legal order by (i) making the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights legally binding by: (i) granting it “the same legal value as the Treaties”; (ii) authorizing EU accession to the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR); and (iii) recognizing that fundamental rights, derived from common constitutional traditions and the ECHR, constitute general principles of EU law.³ As proclaimed by Article 51.1 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights, fundamental rights apply primarily to the institutions and bodies of the European Union, in compliance with the principle of subsidiarity. As regards the Member States of the EU, fundamental rights are only binding on them when they are implementing Union law. As

¹ The terminology used by the EU in the field of rights protection is oscillating between the notions of “fundamental rights” and “human rights”. The term “fundamental rights” is usually used to denote the EU's internal system for the protection of rights as is neatly displayed by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. The term “human rights”, in turn, appears in Article 2 of the TEU, defining the foundational values of the EU, and in the external relations of the EU. In this deliverable, the notion of human rights is used, except where the discussion explicitly concerns the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. See, for the distinction between fundamental rights and human rights in the context of the EU, Williams, ‘Respecting fundamental rights in the new union’ in: C. Barnard (ed.), *The Fundamentals of EU Law Revisited – Assessing the Impact of the Constitutional Debate*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007, p. 71.

² Judgments of 12 November 1969, *Stauder*, 29/69, EU:C:1969:57; of 17 December 1970, *Internationale Handelsgesellschaft* (11/70, EU:C:1970:114) and of 14 May 1974, *Nold v Commission* (4/73, EU:C:1974:51). The story of how the EU's system of rights has evolved in EU law since the judgments by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) in these three cases at the turn of the 1970s, and through the adoption of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union in 2000 and the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon in 2009, to the present day, has already been told numerous times to obviate even a brief repetition. For a concise overview of the development of fundamental rights in EU law, see e.g. Paul Craig and Grainne de Burca, *EU law. Text, Cases, Materials*. Oxford 2020, Chapter 12.

³ Article 6 (ex Article 6 TEU) as a whole provides as follows:

Article 6 (ex Article 6 TEU)

1. The Union recognises the rights, freedoms and principles set out in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union of 7 December 2000, as adapted at Strasbourg, on 12 December 2007, which shall have the same legal value as the Treaties.

The provisions of the Charter shall not extend in any way the competences of the Union as defined in the Treaties. The rights, freedoms and principles in the Charter shall be interpreted in accordance with the general provisions in Title VII of the Charter governing its interpretation and application and with due regard to the explanations referred to in the Charter, that set out the sources of those provisions.

2. The Union shall accede to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. Such accession shall not affect the Union's competences as defined in the Treaties.

3. Fundamental rights, as guaranteed by the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and as they result from the constitutional traditions common to the Member States, shall constitute general principles of the Union's law.

explanations relating to Charter of Fundamental Rights⁴ display, the Court of Justice of the European Union has confirmed this in its established case law since the late 1980s so that the requirement to respect fundamental rights defined in the context of the Union is only binding on the Member States when they act in the scope of Union law.⁵

On the other hand, there is the external EU human rights regime. Since the entry into force of the Treaty of Amsterdam in 1999, respect for human rights has been a legal condition for accession to the EU.⁶ This condition was bolstered in the context of the Union's enlargement to the east in the early 2000s, and has been further entrenched ever since. Following the Lisbon Treaty, Article 3(5) TEU also provides that the EU shall contribute "to the protection of human rights" in its relations with the wider world, while Article 21(1) TEU provides that the EU's action on the international scene shall be guided by the principles of "democracy, the rule of law, the universality and indivisibility of human rights and fundamental freedoms, respect for human dignity, the principles of equality and solidarity" among others. In practice, the EU has included human rights clauses in external agreements dealing with trade, development and association relationships.⁷ However, although human rights clauses abound in international agreements entered into by the EU, their actual effectiveness and implementation have left

⁴ Explanations relating to the Charter of Fundamental Rights, *OJ C 303, 14.12.2007, pp. 17–35*.

⁵ See e.g. judgment of 13 July 1989, Case 5/88 Wachauf [1989] ECR 2609; judgment of 18 June 1991, Case C-260/89 ERT [1991] ECR I-2925; judgment of 18 December 1997, Case C-309/96 Annibaldi [1997] ECR I-7493. See also, more recently, judgment of Case C-769/22 Commission v Hungary, although the question of whether the European Commission may rely on an infringement of Article 2 TEU in the context of an action for failure to fulfil obligations has not yet been clearly settled by the CJEU.

⁶ Article 47 TEU, which sets out the accession procedure, largely codifies the so-called Copenhagen criteria which the European Council adopted at its Copenhagen meeting in 1993. According to the Copenhagen criteria, EU membership requires that the candidate country demonstrates "stability of institutions guaranteeing democracy, the rule of law, human rights and respect for and protection of minorities". The Copenhagen criteria are now reflected in paragraph 1 of Article 49 TEU according to which "(a)ny European State which respects the values referred to in Article 2 and is committed to promoting them may apply to become a member of the Union". Paragraph 2 of Article 49 TEU provides that "(t)he conditions of eligibility agreed upon by the European Council shall be taken into account", thereby alluding to the Copenhagen criteria.

⁷ The EU's actions in the international arena are subject to judicial control by the Court of Justice of the European Union under the procedure prescribed by Article 218(11) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU), according to which a Member State or core EU institution (Commission, Council, Parliament) may request the CJEU's opinion as to an envisaged international agreement's compatibility with EU primary law. As displayed by Opinion 2/13 by the Court of Justice on the proposed accession of the EU to the European Convention of Human Rights (ECHR), the Court's judicial control can also extend to envisaged human rights in the external arena. In Opinion 2/13, the Court held that the proposed accession agreement to the ECHR was contrary to EU law due to reasons connected in various ways to the autonomy of the EU legal order and the position of the CJEU itself as the final arbiter of all EU law matters. For more detailed discussion, see e.g. Halberstam, "It's the Autonomy, Stupid!" A Modest Defense of Opinion 2/13 on EU Accession to the ECHR, and the Way Forward, 16 *German Law Journal* (2015) 105-146; Krenn, Autonomy and effectiveness as common concerns: a path to ECHR accession after Opinion 2/13 16 *German Law Journal* (2015) 147-167; Spaventa, A very fearful court? The protection of fundamental rights in the European Union after opinion 2/13, 22 *Maastricht journal of European and comparative law* (2015) 35-56.

much to be desired. There has usually been a lack of formal suspension of a treaty solely on the basis of human rights violations as the EU has only very exceptionally, in cases such as Myanmar and Sri Lanka, imposed sanctions or withdrawn trade concessions for human rights violations.⁸

However, there has been a significant discrepancy between the internal and external EU fundamental and human rights regimes because of the EU's limited competence to protect and promote fundamental rights within the EU, including to react to its internal fundamental rights problems. Namely, despite the idea that Article 2 TEU lists respect for human rights as one of the values on which the EU is founded and Article 3 TEU adds to this by setting out the goals and objectives of the EU to promote its values, including respect for human rights, the founding treaties of the EU do not provide the EU with any general power to protect and promote fundamental rights. Moreover, fundamental rights may not have the effect of extending the competences and tasks which the Treaties confer on the Union as is explicitly confirmed by Article 51, paragraph 2, of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. Thus, there cannot be any general requirement or even possibility for the EU to mainstream fundamental rights across its internal measures and policies as there is for its external actions and policies pursuant to Article 3(5) TEU.

This asymmetry between the internal and external fundamental and human rights regimes of the EU has given rise to debate over a “double standard” in the EU's approach to human rights. One level of this debate has related to the EU's unequal monitoring of compliance with human rights by a candidate country as compared to a Member State. In essence, the EU has been accused of having more stringent human rights scrutiny over the candidate countries while avoiding placing the EU institutions and the Member States under equally strict control.⁹ This structural discrepancy between the internal and external EU human rights regimes has undermined the credibility of the EU human rights policy both externally and internally.

However, this discrepancy between internal and external human rights regimes has also contributed positively to the evolution of human rights in the EU as it has also impelled the EU to pay attention to its own internal human rights system and its monitoring mechanisms of the

⁸ See e.g. Paul Craig and Grainne de Burca, *EU Law, Text, Cases, Materials*, Sixth Edition, Oxford, 2015, p. 393.

⁹ See e.g. Grainne de Búrca, “The Road Not Taken: The European Union as a Global Human Rights Actor”, 105 *American Journal of International Law* (2011) 649-693.

EU's foundational values under Article 2. It is also noteworthy that one major catalyst for the development of the EU's internal fundamental rights regime has been the process of enlargement of the Union from the early 2000s onwards with its stricter level of scrutiny of candidate countries for their respect for EU values and their commitment to promoting them.¹⁰

3.2 Human rights in a turbulent geopolitical landscape: trends that are likely to shape the protection and promotion of human rights

As the title of Deliverable 7.7 displays, it is set to reflect “geopolitical issues”, including addressing the question of what role geopolitics plays in strategy, resources and reach. According to the HRJust Grant Agreement, it is also preferable to take geopolitical elements into consideration when formulating recommendations for a global system for human rights and democracy.

Therefore, it is necessary to provide an overview of those trends and challenges that are likely to shape and direct the protection and promotion of fundamental and human rights, including the EU's and its Member States' use of human rights justifications, both internally and externally in the EU in coming years.

At the outset, it should be noted that neither the original project proposal submitted to the European Commission nor the Grant Agreement identify those “geopolitical issues and elements” that may influence the EU's and its Member States' use of human rights justifications. In addition, after the entry into force of the Grant Agreement and the start of the HRJust project in March 2023, the geopolitical situation has been in great turmoil. In all parts of the world, including Europe, established institutions and relationships are undergoing profound transformations. There is mounting geopolitical instability and increasing challenges to human rights, the rule of law and democracy worldwide. In short, human rights are under great stress, and this also applies to the rule of law and democracy which are closely intertwined with human rights.¹¹

¹⁰ See e.g. Bruno de Witte, “The impact of enlargement on the Constitution of the European Union”, in *The Enlargement of the European Union*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2003, p. 209, noting already in 2003 that “some important intra-EU constitutional reforms, particularly in the field of fundamental rights protection, might not have occurred, or at least not in the same form, if it had not been for the EU's strong affirmation of these fundamental values in the pre-accession context”.

¹¹ Venice Commission, *The Updated Rule of Law Checklist*, 16 December 2025, CDL-AD(2025)002, paras. 21-23.

In this increasingly fragmented and unpredictable landscape of geopolitics, the following trends and challenges appear to be most relevant to human rights justifications by the EU and to its actions and policies in the field of human rights in general. It needs emphasis that the following trends and challenges are interrelated to some extent. They also tend to affect the fields of migration, climate change and COVID/epidemic challenges in various ways. Moreover, counteracting climate change and environmental degradation is central to preventing the emergence of pandemics such as COVID-19, including all the problems related to human rights and democracy that pandemics and other health crises can give rise to. Climate change and pandemics like COVID-19 are also significant drivers of both voluntary migration and asylum. In addition, although some of the following trends and challenges are more directly related to rule of law and democracy, they have also significant implications on the protection and promotion of human rights due to the interdependence of human rights with the rule of law and democracy.

THE RULE OF LAW, DEMOCRACY AND THE RULES-BASED INTERNATIONAL ORDER ARE INCREASINGLY BEING CHALLENGED

§ Both the Russian war in Ukraine, the Gaza destruction, the US/Israeli war on Iran, the capture and removal of Maduro from Venezuela violate international law.

§ There is an increasing international trend toward regional spheres of power thinking that challenges and disrupts the rules-based international order.

§ Authoritarianism, as it gains a foothold, challenges the rule of law and democracy at both the national and the international level.

§ This is a result of democratic backsliding by elected leaders and increased political polarization.¹²

§ Economic inequality has been increasing over the years in both the EU and other countries.¹³ While global inequality between countries seems

¹² See e.g. Staffan Ingemar Lindberg “Democratic backsliding reaches western democracies, with U.S. decline “unprecedented”” (17 March 2026, University of Gothenburg) at <https://www.gu.se/en/news/democratic-backsliding-reaches-western-democracies-with-us-decline-unprecedented>. Also see Marina Nord, David Altman, Tiago Fernandes, Ana Good God, and Staffan I. Lindberg. 2026. Democracy Report 2026: Unraveling The Democratic Era? University of Gothenburg: V-Dem Institute.

¹³ See e.g. UN 75 2020 and beyond, Shaping our future together, “Inequality – Bridging the Divide”. Concerning Sweden see e.g. Statistics Sweden, 2025-05-22, “Income inequality has increased since the 1990s” (Income and taxes: Income distribution 1991–2023) <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/household-finances/household-income-assets-and-debts/income-and-tax-statistics/pong/statistical->

to have improved, wealth has concentrated largely at the top. Wealth concentration rather than inequality related to salary income is a key. Major drivers are technological advancements and globalization.

DEMOCRATIC BACKSLIDING

There are several major trends concerning backsliding¹⁴

§ Backsliding in some traditionally stable democracies, in particular the US.

§ Significant reversals and often breakdown of democracy and the rule of law can be seen in countries that successfully democratized during the late 20th and early 21st centuries. A reference can here be made to e.g. Hungary and Poland although the latter is now actively working to restore the rule of law.

§ There has been a deepening of autocracy in already autocratic states.

§ Freedom of Expression shows the most drastic global decline, and has been the most common target among leaders becoming more autocratic over the past 25 years. Another key target is the rule of law and checks on the abuse of power.

§ There are some positive notes concerning democracy with large countries such as Brazil and Poland deepening their democratic processes, and others providing expanded media freedom.

CHANGING PATTERNS OF MIGRATION

The flow of migrants internationally as well as to EU Member States is expected to grow in the coming years¹⁵

§ Concerning the EU and other parts of the world, the Russian war of aggression against Ukraine is one reason. There are also wider trends, namely the overall worsening of the security situation (e.g. the situation in Gaza, the war against Iran) creating uncertainty going forward. What

[news/income-distribution-19912023/#:~:text=Statistical%20news%20from%20Statistics%20Sweden,changes%20within%20each%20income%20decile.](#)

¹⁴ See fn 12.

¹⁵ See e.g. McAuliffe, M. and L.A. Oucho (Eds.), 2024. *WORLD MIGRATION REPORT 2024*. International Organization For Migration (IOM), Geneva, 1-2.

can also be seen are uneven distinct migration patterns shaped by economic, geographic, demographic and other factors, resulting in migration “corridors” developed over many years. The largest corridors tend to be from developing countries to larger economies, such as the United States of America, the United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia and Germany, as well as corridors that reflect protracted conflict and related displacement, such as from the Syrian Arab Republic to Turkey.¹⁶

There are important interactions between migration and gender worldwide. These relate to refugee migration, family migration, marriage migration and labour migration. There are often disparities concerning gender related to stereotypes, access to information, the digital divide and regular migration pathways, disparities that can be counteracted through conscious policies or exacerbated. This has led to a call for gender-responsive migration governance as indicated in the Global Compact for Migration.¹⁷ Or as indicated by IOM “Adopting a gender-responsive approach to migration governance is thus a necessity to empower migrants of all genders and further gender equality more generally as the “prerequisite for a better world”.¹⁸

§ There is also the issue of an expected increase in climate change-driven migration and asylum. As climate records continue to be broken, the specific future impacts are not entirely clear, but major impacts are expected unless e.g. adequate preventative actions related to carbon emissions and green technology uptake, as well as preparedness actions, such as disaster risk reduction work, are undertaken. Certain multilateral processes on climate change, such as multilateral mobility frameworks agreed by States (such as the Pacific Regional Framework on Climate Mobility), provide for some optimism on cooperation going forward.¹⁹

¹⁶ Ibid, 3.

¹⁷ See McAuliffe, M. and L.A. Ocho (Eds.), 2024. WORLD MIGRATION REPORT 2024. International Organization For Migration (IOM), Geneva, 188-195.

¹⁸ Ibid, 195.

¹⁹ Ibid, 1-2.

§ Increase of both voluntary migration as well as asylum is coupled with the rise of a security-based migration agenda with sustained but also excessive attention by the EU and its Member States to security issues in relation to migration, especially refugee migration (e.g. the new EU Pact on Migration and Asylum);

CLIMATE CHANGE IS AN EXISTENTIAL RISK TO HUMAN RIGHTS

§ Rapidly accelerating climate change has potentially devastating consequences for all aspects of life, including human rights, of those most affected by the impacts now as well as of future generations.²⁰ While the vast majority of human rights stand to be affected, threats to the right to life, health, water, food and housing appear particularly serious and already manifest. In addition, while estimates of future so-called climate migrants widely differ at present,²¹ climate change can influence migration drivers, patterns, countries of destination, and the protection of the rights of migrants and asylum seekers. The consequences of climate change are also likely to worsen inequalities by exacerbating existing vulnerabilities. The above clearly demonstrates the urgent need for a human rights-based approach to climate change and to climate action.

§ At the same time, there is also increasing rights-awareness in the context of climate change given ongoing climate litigation as well as civil society's advocacy and public protests, which not infrequently rely on human rights arguments. This might make it more likely that, in the future, EU institutions and Member States will resort more often to HRJs or related notions, if only reactively.

§ The current energy crisis caused by the ongoing conflict in Iran and the closure of the Strait of Hormuz could be a catalyst for a green transition that promotes and protects human rights;²² alternatively, HRJs

²⁰ See, among many, S. Humphreys (ed.), *Human Rights and Climate Change* (2010); and United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), *Climate Change and Human Rights* (2015).

²¹ See European Commission, *Forecasting Climate Migration - How Much Do We Really Know?* (2025).

²² Craig Hanson and Jessica Isaacs, *As Iran War Strains Fuel Supplies, Clean Energy Is Secure Energy*, World Resources Institute, 10 April 2026, <<https://www.wri.org/insights/iran-war-clean-energy-benefits>>; and Zia Weise, *Fossil fuels? No thanks. Why Trump's Iran war is pushing EU toward renewables*, Politico Europe, 18

could be used to support short-term fossil fuel solutions as has happened following the Russian Federation's invasion of Ukraine.

AI AND DIGITALIZATION CONTINUE TO BE IMPORTANT FACTORS

§ Major advances in AI, especially generative AI tools have increasingly filled the world stage, impacting a wide range of sectors and occupations. Some call for the embracing of such tools while others such as some of the creators of the latest generative AI tools caution against the increasing proliferation of AI technologies throughout our societies. There are both potential positive as well as negative impacts in the fields of migration, health care and climate change.²³

4. Competences and human rights justifications of the EU in the fields of Covid, Migration and Climate

4.1 General observations

As already noted, the founding Treaties of the European Union do not provide the EU any general power to protect and promote fundamental rights internally within the EU legal order. Fundamental rights also fail to have the effect of extending the competences and tasks which the Treaties confer on the Union. Instead, the internal role of the EU in the field of human rights may arise only within the limits of its powers determined by the Treaties. The situation is different as regards external EU competence and the power to conclude international agreements with third countries or international organisations due to the above-mentioned Article 3(5) and Article 21(1) TEU.

March 2026, <<https://www.politico.eu/article/fossil-fuels-no-thanks-why-donald-trump-iran-war-pushing-the-eu-toward-renewables/>>.

²³ Ibid, 2.

Yet, the EU is founded on the principle of conferred powers and, therefore, the EU may only act when there is a legal basis for action provided in the founding Treaties, i.e. the EU can only have attributed competence. Thus, Article 4 TEU provides that competences not conferred on the EU remain with the Member States, while Article 5 TEU states that the limits of the EU competences are governed by the principle of conferral. Moreover, there are different categories of the EU competence – exclusive, shared, parallel and supporting competence – and the choice of legal basis also determines the procedures by which EU measures may be adopted in the EU. In the context of external relations, the type of competence will also determine whether it is the EU alone, the EU together with its Member States or in parallel with them, or the Member States alone which take part in international actions or policy-making or enter into international agreements.

Against this background, an analysis of EU competences and human rights justifications in the fields covered by HRJust WPs 4-6, i.e. Covid, Migration and Climate is needed with reference to those four questions regarding which Deliverable 7.7 is required to address.

4.2 EU Migration Governance: Competences, Human Rights Justifications and the Internal-External Divide

4.2.1 EU Competence and Political Discretion in Migration

Migration is a shared competence between the EU and its Member States, yet the breadth of EU legislative powers means that little in this field remains purely national in character. Articles 77–79 TFEU confer far-reaching legislative powers on the EU institutions. These provisions empower the Union to adopt measures on border control, asylum, and immigration, including the harmonisation of national laws and the establishment of common procedures. Member States only retain competence over the volume of admission of third-country nationals and aspects of integration policy.

EU primary law establishes rather vague and open-ended standards, granting political actors wide discretion to shape migration policy – even within a formally rights-based framework. On the one hand, Article 79 TFEU emphasises control-oriented goals such as preventing irregular migration and strengthening external borders. On the other hand, Article 78 TFEU imposes binding obligations relating to international protection, including non-refoulement and compliance with international law. These objectives are not hierarchically ordered but must be balanced in the legislative process, leaving significant room for political

decision-making. As Thym observes, the Treaty drafters made a conscious choice to lay down broad competences, thereby allowing EU institutions to develop migration policy gradually without a politically cumbersome Treaty revision.²⁴ Flexibility serves effectiveness in crisis situations well, where the political sensitivity of migration tends to favour executive decision-making over deliberative or rights-oriented procedures.²⁵

4.2.2 Human Rights Justifications in EU Migration Law

Human rights play a formally important but practically limited role in EU migration governance. While the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and international human rights obligations are part of the EU's constitutional framework, they function primarily as background principles. Legislative acts in the field of migration routinely invoke human rights dimensions — references to dignity, non-refoulement, and the right to asylum appear in recitals and preambles — but these invocations do not consistently translate into rights-based reasoning in practice.

The activation of the Temporary Protection Directive (TPD) in 2022 for persons fleeing Ukraine illustrates this pattern.²⁶ EU institutions and Member States framed the response primarily through humanitarian considerations, solidarity, security, and European political responsibility, rather than explicit human rights claims.²⁷ Human rights were acknowledged in passing, as a contextual backdrop, but the activation decision was grounded in geopolitical and solidarity arguments. The Directive itself is constructed around the category of 'displaced persons' rather than 'refugees', which enables the EU to offer protection without committing to a stronger rights-based narrative.

This approach has concrete consequences. Sweden and Finland demonstrate different reception policies.²⁸ Finland adopted a relatively inclusive approach, granting personal identity numbers, access to municipal registration, and healthcare largely on equal terms with citizens. Sweden applied a more restrictive interpretation, initially excluding beneficiaries from

²⁴ D Thym, *European Migration Law* (Oxford University Press, 2023) 29.

²⁵ D Thym, "'The Refugee Crisis' as a Challenge of Legal Design and Institutional Legitimacy" (2016) 53 *Common Market Law Review* 1545–1548; B de Witte and E Tsourdi, 'Confrontation on Relocation – The Court of Justice Endorses the Emergency Scheme for Compulsory Relocation of Asylum Seekers within the European Union: Slovak Republic and Hungary v. Council' (2018) 55 *Common Market Law Review* 1458; A Wallerman Ghavanini, 'The CJEU's Give-and-Give Relationship with Executive Actors in Times of Crisis' (2023) 2 *European Law Open*.

²⁶ Council Implementing Decision (EU) 2022/382 (Ukraine TPD activation); Commission Communication COM/2022/107 final, *European Solidarity with Refugees and those Fleeing the War in Ukraine*.

²⁷ M Westlund and O Chernenko, 'Why the Temporary Protection Directive was Activated: Solidarity, Geopolitics, and Humanitarian Considerations' (2026) 2 *Europarättslig tidskrift*.

²⁸ M Westlund and O Chernenko (2026).

population registration, limiting adults to emergency healthcare, and providing only minimal financial support comparable to that of asylum seekers. These divergent outcomes illustrate how the absence of binding human rights standards enables wide variation in the level of protection actually afforded.

4.2.3 The Internal-External Divide and Accountability Gaps

A central tension in EU migration governance lies in the divergence between the EU's internal constitutional role and its external geopolitical conduct. Internally, the EU develops and harmonises law through formal legislative procedures subject to parliamentary oversight and judicial review. Externally, it operates in a space where legal constraints are considerably weaker, and political bargaining plays a stronger role. This produces what might be described as an 'internal–external divide' in human rights protection: standards applicable within the EU legal order are frequently not mirrored in the EU's dealings with third countries.

The EU–Turkey Statement of 2016 is a good example of this dilemma. Through this arrangement, the EU outsourced responsibility for Syrian refugees to Turkey in exchange for financial and political concessions, bypassing formal legislative procedures and the safeguards they entail. When affected individuals sought judicial review before the CJEU, the Court declared it had no jurisdiction, on the basis that the Statement was attributable to the Member States.²⁹ As a result, informal migration arrangements structured in a legally ambiguous manner effectively evade both parliamentary oversight and judicial scrutiny, while producing concrete effects on the rights of individuals.

The external dimension of EU migration governance demonstrates how the EU increasingly exercises influence through bilateral and informal arrangements with third countries. Cooperation through readmission agreements, financial assistance, mobility partnerships, and border management mechanisms allows the EU to externalise migration control beyond its territorial borders. These arrangements strengthen executive discretion because they are frequently developed outside ordinary legislative procedures and with limited parliamentary oversight or judicial scrutiny. The political sensitivity of migration governance has therefore contributed to a shift toward flexible and informal forms of cooperation that prioritise effectiveness and migration control over transparency and accountability.³⁰

²⁹ Cases T-192/16 NF v European Council; T-193/16 NG v European Council; T-257/16 NM v European Council.

³⁰ M Westlund, "Law as the Executive Likes it: How the European Court of Justice Accommodates the Executive in Migration's External Dimension," in C Eckes, P Leino Sandberg and AW Ghavanini (eds.), *The Dynamics of Powers in the European Union*, 2024, Hart Publishing.

This development also risks diffusing legal and political responsibility for potential human rights violations. By transferring migration control to third countries and relying on informal cooperation mechanisms, the EU and its Member States can distance themselves from the direct exercise of authority while still shaping migration outcomes in practice. The increasing use of legally ambiguous arrangements therefore weakens the effectiveness of traditional rule of law safeguards within the EU legal order. Individuals affected by externalised migration measures often face significant obstacles in identifying the responsible actor, accessing judicial remedies, or challenging decisions that produce concrete consequences for their rights.³¹

Geopolitics further conditions these dynamics. The swift activation of the TPD for Ukrainians, in contrast to asylum seekers during the migration crisis, reveals that EU migration policy serves both humanitarian and strategic functions. The proximity of Ukraine to EU political and economic structures, combined with the need to demonstrate unity against Russia's invasion, shaped a response that blended solidarity narratives with migration governance.³² Similar situations have thus produced markedly different legal responses, depending on the geopolitical alignment of the affected population.

4.3 The EU and Climate Change: Competences, Human Rights Justifications and Extraterritoriality

4.3.1 EU Competence in the Area of Climate Change

While the 1957 Treaty of Rome contained no mention of the environment, increasing awareness in the following years and decades about the importance of a safe, clean and healthy environment as well as about the limitations of exclusively national actions went hand in hand with an expansion of the powers of the EU in the area of environmental protection and an increased role for the European Parliament. Since the 1987 Single European Act, environmental protection has found a Treaty basis and is today a **shared competence** of the

³¹ AP García, 'The Distribution of Powers Between EU Institutions for Conducting External Affairs through Non-Binding Instruments' (2016) 1 *European Papers* 116; N Idriz and M Fink, 'Effective Judicial Protection in the External Dimension of the EU's Migration and Asylum Policies?' (2021) *TMC Asser Institute for International & European Law Asser Research Paper Series*; T Spijkerboer, 'Bifurcation of people, bifurcation of law: Externalization of migration policy before the EU Court of Justice,' (2018) 31 *Journal of refugee studies* 2.

³² M Westlund and O Chernenko (2026).

EU and its Member States. This is made clear in Articles 4, 11, and 191-193 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).

The fight against climate change undisputedly falls within the protection of the environment and Article 191(1) TFEU explicitly includes, among the objectives to be pursued by the EU environmental policy, “promoting measures at international level to deal with regional or worldwide environmental problems, and in particular combating climate change”. The EU and its Member States also share competence in other areas related to climate change, such as that of energy (Article 194 TFEU). Moreover, the EU is making increasing efforts to mainstream climate considerations and objectives in further policy areas – e.g., transport, agriculture and fisheries, social policy and the internal market.³³

In practice, due to the global nature of climate change and the need to act collectively to mitigate and adapt to it, the EU has assumed a **most prominent role** in combatting climate change. Accordingly, the EU is a party to the UNFCCC, the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement; it plays a leading role in climate change negotiations at the international level; it has adopted overarching common emission reduction goals; it has promoted market-based instruments; and it has developed increasingly detailed legislative acts setting standards, among others, on energy efficiency, renewable energy, land use and forestry, transport, and the protection of biodiversity and nature restoration.³⁴ This evolution has strengthened both the role of the EU as a regional actor (which has assumed functions that were originally performed at the national level) and the role of the EU as a global actor, as the EU is by now identified as one of the major players in climate negotiations and climate action at the international level. On the relationship between the EU internal and external competences in this area, see in more detail section 4.3.3 *infra*.

4.3.2 *The EU and Human Rights Justifications in the Area of Climate Change*

The peculiar role of the EU has an impact on the use of HRJs. Indeed, the EU might act both as a monitor of the use of HRJs by Member States (see, in this respect, Deliverable D7.6) and as a user of HRJs itself. It is the latter role that is more specifically considered here, by examining whether and to what extent EU institutions have had recourse to HRJs in performing

³³ European Commission, *Climate Mainstreaming*, <https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/performance-and-reporting/horizontal-priorities/green-budgeting/climate-mainstreaming_en> accessed 26 January 2026.

³⁴ For an overview of the policies, laws and actions adopted by the EU in the fight against climate change, see, among others, Tim Rayner *et al.* (eds.), *HANDBOOK ON EUROPEAN UNION CLIMATE CHANGE POLICY AND POLITICS* (2023); and Edwin Woerdman, Martha Roggenkamp & Marijn Holwerda (eds.), *ESSENTIAL EU CLIMATE LAW*, 2nd ed. (2021).

their functions in the area of climate change, particularly in adopting legislative texts and in the context of proceedings before the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU).

At the outset, some preliminary observations on the climate change-human rights interface can be made that influences the configuration of HRJs in the area of climate change. On the one hand, the interconnections between climate change and human rights are by now evident³⁵ – a circumstance that could encourage the use of HRJs in relation to climate change policy. On the other, the integration of human rights in climate change legal instruments has lagged behind compared to the reality on the ground. The growing success of human rights-based climate litigation is a further variable that might have an impact on these dynamics.³⁶

In another respect, the diffuse impacts of climate change on everyone’s human rights makes the general typology of HRJs elaborated for this Project (Deliverable D3.2) at times of complex application, as it might be difficult to identify a conflict between the rights of specific individuals or groups. The fact that climate change might be construed as often affecting interests in addition to rights (see again Deliverable D3.2) and the idea that political, democratically-mandated bodies should be afforded a wide margin of discretion in devising climate policies and accommodating competing needs³⁷ can contribute to explain why – as is shown below – **related notions** were found to be more common than HRJs in the area of climate change.

As illustrated more in-depth in Deliverables D2.2 and D7.6,³⁸ by “related notions” we refer to instances where, rather than referring to human rights *sensu stricto*, the legal acts in question mention concepts or principles that are nonetheless connected with human rights as justifications for the adoption of the act and for certain policy choices. Examples in the area of climate change include sustainable development and the creation of jobs as well as the protection of health, without mentioning the right to work or the right to health. While this trend is not unique to climate change (having been detected in other thematic areas of this Project), different reasons might explain why governments opt for related notions rather than HRJs.

³⁵ See above fn 20.

³⁶ J. Peel and H. M. Osofsky, “A Rights Turn in Climate Change Litigation?”, *Transnational Environmental Law*, 7:1 (2018), pp. 37-67.

³⁷ Chiara Tea Antoniazzi, *Report on Climate-Related Litigation and the Separation of Powers* (last updated January 2026).

³⁸ For an illustration of the concept of “related notions” for the purposes of this Project, see Chiara Tea Antoniazzi and Caterina Milo, *Report on the Concept of “Related Notions”* (last updated December 2025).

Below, sub-sections i-v first examine in more detail key EU legislative instruments in the area of climate change, focusing – in addition to foundational acts like the European Green Deal and European Climate Law – on those legislative measures which have been considered more controversial because of their alleged negative impacts on the human rights of EU citizens and of citizens of third countries. It is therefore particularly interesting to observe whether the preambles of such acts, the explanatory memoranda of the related Commission’s proposals and other pertinent documents include human rights justifications (HRJs).

After sub-sections i-v analysing HRJs in key EU legislative instruments in the field of climate change, a closer look at HRJs in the context of climate litigation is made in sub-section vi.

i. European Green Deal and European Climate Law

Both the Communication from the Commission outlining the European Green Deal³⁹ and the so-called European Climate Law⁴⁰ contain rather scant explicit references to human rights, whereas mentions of so-called **related notions** are more common.

Accordingly, it is stated that the **European Green Deal** “aims to protect, conserve and enhance the EU’s natural capital, and protect the *health and well-being of citizens* from environment-related risks and impacts. At the same time, this transition must be *just and inclusive*. It must put people first, and pay attention to the regions, *industries and workers* who will face the greatest challenges” (emphases added).

The **European Climate Law** explicitly mentions human rights only at recital 6, which states that “[t]his Regulation respects the fundamental rights and observes the principles recognised by the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (CFREU), in particular Article 37 thereof ...”. Therefore, it includes human rights in a statement of compliance rather than in a justification. On the other hand, the preamble more broadly refers to various notions related to human rights as drivers of the act: in addition to recall (at recital 2) the aims of the European Green Deal mentioned above, further recitals mention “high-quality jobs” and “sustainable growth” (recital 4); expand on the need to protect health (recital 5); and refer to the safeguard of “welfare, prosperity, the economy, health, food systems ...” (recital 9).

³⁹ Communication from the Commission of 11 December 2019, COM(2019) 640 final.

⁴⁰ Regulation (EU) 2021/1119 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2021 establishing the framework for achieving climate neutrality and amending Regulations (EC) No 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999.

Overall, HRJs in the strict sense appear to play a limited role as a foundation for the European Green Deal and the European Climate Law, but various related notions are used as the basis for the adoption of the acts. What can also be noted is that, either explicitly or implicitly, the human rights or related interests/concerns only of EU citizens appear to be taken into account. The external dimension of the EU climate policy is considered by the European Green Deal essentially in terms of diplomacy, trade policy, and development aid (para. 3).

ii. The Renewable Energy Directive and the Taxonomy Regulation

The **Renewable Energy Directive**, as revised in 2018 (RED II)⁴¹ and 2023 (RED III)⁴², has been criticised because of its qualification of forest biomass as a source of low-carbon renewable energy and the alleged ineffectiveness of the Directive’s sustainability criteria for forest biomass harvesting.⁴³ Such criticism has also led to legal proceedings before the CJEU (*Sabo and Others v Parliament and Council*), which were premised, among others, on the alleged violation of multiple rights protected by the CFREU, including the rights to respect for private and family life, religion, property, health and environmental protection, in light of the risks of increased deforestation and increased GHG emissions.

Similarly to the European Green Deal and the European Climate Law, RED II and RED III do not employ HRJs in the strict sense, but they make use of related notions. Accordingly, **RED II** rather generally refers to the fact that greater use of renewable energy provides “environmental, social and health benefits as well as major opportunities for employment and regional development” (recital 3 of the preamble). More specifically with regard to the use of biofuels, the creation of jobs is listed as a relevant justification (preamble of RED II, recital 85).

Likewise, the preamble of **RED III** refers to the importance of renewable energy in addressing energy poverty and producing “broad socio-economic benefits”, including the creation of new jobs and the growth of local industries (recital 2). This echoes the Commission’s proposal for a revision of RED II,⁴⁴ whose explanatory memorandum states that

⁴¹ Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the promotion of the use of energy from renewable sources (recast).

⁴² Directive (EU) 2023/2413 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 October 2023 amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 and Directive 98/70/EC as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652.

⁴³ See, e.g., ClientEarth and others, *Unsustainable and Ineffective: Why EU Forest Biomass Standards Won’t Stop Destruction* (May 2021).

⁴⁴ Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive (EU) 2018/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 of the European Parliament and of the

“[t]his revision of REDII is essential ... to protect our environment and health, reduce our energy dependency, and contribute to the EU’s technological and industrial leadership along with the creation of jobs and economic growth” (para. 1; see also para. 3). Regarding human rights *sensu stricto*, they are mentioned explicitly to confirm that the revised Directive would comply with the CFREU (and specifically be in line with its Article 37), rather than as a justification as such for the review (para. 3). With regard to biomass specifically, the fact that “[a] coordinated response of more than 38,000 participants requested removing biomass from the list of renewable resources and limiting the use for bioenergy to locally available waste and residues” is rather cursorily dismissed, as the “targeted strengthening” of existing sustainability criteria is presented as the best option (para. 3).

The so-called **Taxonomy Regulation**,⁴⁵ which lays down the requirements for economic activities to be considered environmentally sustainable, and the related **Commission Delegated Regulation 2022/1214**, which details the relevant screening criteria for certain economic activities, have also been called into question in light of the Delegated Regulation’s classification of fossil gas and nuclear energy as environmentally sustainable. While the legal actions brought against the Delegated Regulation, including by Austria⁴⁶ and various environmental NGOs,⁴⁷ have mostly focused on the act’s conflict with environmental principles and with climate change mitigation and adaptation objectives, human rights-based arguments similar to those advanced in *Sabo and Others* could also have been made.

For its part, the preamble of the Taxonomy Regulation as well as the related Commission’s proposal are centred on sustainable development, which is one of the related notions most frequently recurring in the context of the justification of climate policy and norms. On the other hand, human rights in the strict sense are again not referred to as justification for the policy, but they are mentioned only insofar as compliance with international and EU human rights standards, especially in the field of labour, is required for an activity to be considered environmentally sustainable (recital 35 of the preamble of the Taxonomy Regulation; see also para. 3 of the explanatory memorandum in the Commission’s proposal). As for the specific qualification of fossil gas and nuclear activities as environmentally sustainable, the main arguments made were – quite paradoxically – environment- and climate-related (i.e., that these

Council and Directive 98/70/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the promotion of energy from renewable sources, and repealing Council Directive (EU) 2015/652, 14 July 2021, COM(2021) 557 final.

⁴⁵ Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088.

⁴⁶ Case T-625/22 *Austria v Commission* (action brought on 7 October 2022).

⁴⁷ Case T-214/23 *Greenpeace and Others v Commission* (action brought on 18 April 2023); and Case T-215/23 *ClientEarth and Others v Commission* (action brought on 18 April 2023).

activities accelerate the decarbonisation of the economy and the green transition), although Mr. Dombrovskis, then Executive Vice-President for an Economy that Works for People, also mentioned the need for a “just transition”.⁴⁸

It should also be mentioned that a reduction of the Taxonomy Regulation’s scope of application is foreseen in the first “**Simplification Omnibus package**” put forward by the Commission at the end of February 2025 and aimed at cutting red tape in the fields of sustainability reporting and due diligence.⁴⁹ The proposal builds on the Communication “A simpler and faster Europe: Communication on implementation and simplification”, issued shortly before, according to which the simplification of the relevant regulatory framework is justified, among others, by the need to “boost prosperity and resilience” and to “protect and empower people”.⁵⁰

iii. Deforestation Regulation

The **Deforestation Regulation**⁵¹ is particularly interesting for the purposes of this analysis because of its pronounced external dimension (see also section 4.3.3 *infra*). This is reflected both in the fact that the Regulation is directed at preventing the import to and export from the EU of products that contribute to deforestation and forest degradation; and in the fact that the feared adverse effects on human rights mainly concern people living in third countries. While most environmental NGOs have welcomed the Regulation⁵² and opposed the postponement of its application to 30 December 2025,⁵³ some concerns have been expressed regarding the inability of smallholder producers in developing countries to meet the more stringent requirements and higher costs, thus potentially resulting in job losses and negative ripple

⁴⁸ European Commission, “EU Taxonomy: Commission presents Complementary Climate Delegated Act to accelerate decarbonisation”, Press release, 2 February 2022.

⁴⁹ Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directives (EU) 2022/2464 and (EU) 2024/1760 as regards the dates from which Member States are to apply certain corporate sustainability reporting and due diligence requirements, 26 February 2025, COM(2025) 80 final.

⁵⁰ Communication from the Commission, “A simpler and faster Europe: Communication on implementation and simplification”, 11 February 2025, COM(2025) 47 final.

⁵¹ Regulation (EU) 2023/1115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 31 May 2023 on the making available on the Union market and the export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation and repealing Regulation (EU) No 995/2010.

⁵² WWF, *EU leaders seal deal for groundbreaking law to stop deforestation*, 6 December 2022, <<https://www.wwf.eu/?8350966/EU-leaders-seal-deal-for-groundbreaking-law-to-stop-deforestation>> accessed 26 January 2026.

⁵³ WWF, *225 global groups say ‘Hands off the EU deforestation regulation!’*, 15 October 2024, <<https://www.wwf.eu/?15410891/225-global-groups-say-Hands-off-the-EU-deforestation-regulation>> accessed 26 January 2026.

effects on local communities;⁵⁴ as well as regarding the undue restrictions on indigenous peoples' use of forests.⁵⁵

Human rights and related notions feature prominently in the Deforestation Regulation. Starting with the first recital of its preamble, the Regulation underlines not only how combatting deforestation brings fundamental environmental benefits, but also how “forests provide *subsistence and income* to approximately one third of the world’s population and the destruction of forests has serious consequences for the livelihoods of the *most vulnerable people, including indigenous peoples* and local communities who depend heavily on forest ecosystems” (emphases added). It is also noted how deforestation makes the emergence of new diseases and epidemics more likely, thus threatening human health. The fight against deforestation and forest degradation is also linked to the protection of environmental human rights defenders (recital 7) and to the contribution to sustainable development (recital 20).

EU institutions and EU Member States also show awareness of the human rights risks inherent in the application of the Regulation, by providing for consultation with local stakeholders and full recognition of the rights of **indigenous peoples and local communities** (recital 29; paras. 57-59 put further emphasis on the rights of indigenous people and on the principle of free, prior and informed consent). The Regulation also makes reference to the payment of a “fair price ... to producers, in particular smallholders, so as to enable a living income and effectively address poverty as a root cause of deforestation” (recital 50). Furthermore, human rights are an integral part of the due diligence systems provided for by the Regulation: operators are required to consider violations of international human rights in the country of origin within the risk assessment that they carry out (Article 10(2)(h)) and to report on the consultation with indigenous peoples, local communities, other customary tenure rights holders and NGOs (Article 12(4)(c)). Additionally, cooperation with third countries is also to be based on “strengthen[ing] the rights of forest-dependent communities” (Article 30(3)) and

⁵⁴ See, among others, Eliza Zhunusovaa *et al.*, *Potential Impacts of the Proposed EU Regulation on Deforestation-free Supply Chains on Smallholders, Indigenous Peoples, and Local Communities in Producer Countries Outside the EU*, FOREST POLICY AND ECONOMICS 102817 (2022).

⁵⁵ Romy Klimke, *Out of the Woods? Human Rights and the New EU Regulation on Deforestation*, VERFASSUNGSBLOG, 3 August 2023, <<https://verfassungsblog.de/out-of-the-woods/>> accessed 26 January 2026; ClientEarth and Global Witness, *Upholding human rights in the fight against deforestation*, 6 September 2021, <<https://www.clientearth.org/latest/documents/upholding-human-rights-in-the-fight-against-deforestation/>> accessed 26 January 2026.

on “EU’s development cooperation objectives like poverty alleviation, good governance, human rights” (explanatory memorandum of the Commission’s proposal, para. 1⁵⁶).

Conversely, the Regulation also takes into account the “**legitimate expectations of operators and traders**”, which are explicitly balanced against the protection of the environment (recital 45 of the preamble); and it is on such basis that the application of several provisions of the Regulation is deferred compared to its entry into force.⁵⁷ The same argument has been used, among others, to justify moving forward again the date of application to 30 August 2025 for medium and large companies. Overall, as potentially conflicting human rights concerns are explicitly taken into account in the Regulation and used to justify the policy choices made, much will hinge on implementing acts and on the enforcement of the Regulation.

iv. Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM)

The CBAM is an innovative tool to prevent so-called carbon leakage and ensure that EU limitations on GHG emissions are not circumvented or frustrated by the transfer of production abroad or by the import of cheaper carbon-intensive products in the EU. The instrument has been strongly opposed by developing countries and EU trading partners, which have argued that it conflicts with multiple international legal norms and principles, including State sovereignty, the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities and WTO rules.⁵⁸ While the potentially negative impacts on human rights are more indirect, the right to development and the right to work could be adversely affected, especially of people living in least developed countries with significant exports to the EU.

Unsurprisingly, the main driver of the CBAM is identified with strengthening the decarbonisation process inside and outside the EU, by increasing the carbon price and encouraging other countries to follow a similar approach. Human rights and related notions do

⁵⁶ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the making available on the Union market as well as export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation and repealing Regulation (EU) No 995/2010, 17 November 2021, COM(2021) 706 final.

⁵⁷ Recital 47 of the preamble: “*The limitations on the exercise of the fundamental rights and the protection of the legitimate expectations of operators and traders* resulting from the choice of the cut-off date should be proportionate to, and strictly necessary for, pursuing the general interest objective of environmental protection. To contribute to that objective, this Regulation should not apply to relevant commodities and relevant products produced before the date of entry into force of this Regulation. The deferred application of provisions of this Regulation governing obligations for operators and traders who intend to place relevant commodities and relevant products on the market or to export them also provides them a reasonable period of time to adapt to the new requirements of this Regulation” (emphasis added).

⁵⁸ See, for an overview, Natalie L. Dobson, *(Re)framing Responsibility? Assessing the Division of Burdens Under the EU Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism*, 18(2) UTRECHT LAW REVIEW 162 (2022).

not play a prominent role in justifying the adoption of the CBAM, apart from references to the broader “just and inclusive” transition pursued by the European Green Deal and an assessment of the impact of the CBAM on employment (an impact that is considered limited: see section 3 of the explanatory memorandum in the Commission’s proposal⁵⁹).

Albeit in rather vague terms, the Regulation and the preceding proposal acknowledge that third countries trading with the EU, and especially less developed countries, could be affected; in this respect, continuing dialogue and cooperation with such countries are invoked (recitals 70-72 of the preamble), together with financial support in order to promote the decarbonisation of their industries and their compliance with the requirements of the Regulation (recitals 73-74). However, a proposal by the European Parliament to allocate financial support to least developed countries in an amount equivalent to the revenues from the sale of CBAM certificates was not included in the final version of the Regulation;⁶⁰ also, any potentially adverse impacts of the CBAM abroad are considered in relation to the affected third countries’ economies rather than in relation to their citizens’ rights or interests.

v. Concluding observations on HRJs in EU legislative instruments in the field of climate change

Overall, HRJs in the strict sense appear to play a limited role as driver for the adoption of key EU legislative acts on climate change. On the other hand, it is more common for EU institutions and Member States to use notions related to human rights – such as sustainable development, the protection of health, the promotion of a just transition, and the creation of jobs. As some uses of these concepts can blur the lines between the protection of the public interest and the protection of the rights of individuals and groups, related notions raise similar – in addition to further – issues compared to HRJs.

On the other hand, when human rights are specifically mentioned in the legislative acts examined, this is generally to confirm the compliance of the act in question with EU human rights obligations rather than as a justification for a policy choice. Nonetheless, this is to be

⁵⁹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a carbon border adjustment mechanism, 14 July 2021, COM(2021) 564 final.

⁶⁰ Jakub Bednarek, *Is the EU Realizing an Externally Just Green Transition? A Short Analysis of The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism from the Perspective of the CBDR Principle and the Right to Development of LDCs*, EJIL:TALK!, 31 October 2022, <<https://www.ejiltalk.org/is-the-eu-realizing-an-externally-just-green-transition-a-short-analysis-of-the-carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism-from-the-perspective-of-the-cbdr-principle-and-the-right-to-development-of-lDCs/>> accessed 26 January 2026.

interpreted as a trend rather than as a rule as, for instance, the Deforestation Regulation refers to the rights of different stakeholders to justify the approach and contents of the act.

In any case, the use of HRJs or related notions in climate-related legislative acts appears less problematic than in other areas, as the green transition and the protection of human rights are often aligned. Insofar as potential conflicts between climate action and human rights might arise (e.g., between the decarbonisation process and the right to work or development), a balancing act will need to be carried out in practice between competing rights and needs, but the terms of these legislative acts of a general nature are mostly sufficiently broad to enable an application of the acts that is compatible with human rights.⁶¹ In this respect, for instance, the European Green Deal refers to the creation of a Just Transition Mechanism, which “will also strive to protect the citizens and workers most vulnerable to the transition, providing access to re-skilling programmes, jobs in new economic sectors, or energy-efficient housing” (para. 2.2.1). Accordingly, the implementation level and, possibly, the litigation level assume decisive importance.

vi. HRJs in Climate Litigation

Before the CJEU (or before the national courts asking for preliminary rulings), human rights-based arguments are almost always raised by the individual claimants, while the defendant Member States or EU institutions generally ask the Court to reject the case as **inadmissible** or, in the alternative, unfounded on the merits. Accordingly, the State/EU institution puts forward procedural grounds for inadmissibility (primarily the lack of standing of individuals or NGOs); argues a lack of causality between its actions/omissions and any harm; or maintains that no interference with the rights of the applicant took place or that any interference was not disproportionate.

This trend could depend on the peculiar context of litigation, where Member States and EU institutions generally act as defendants in the proceedings; also, especially before the CJEU, the arguments developed by the parties are not reported at length in the judgments, which makes it more difficult to identify HRJs.

⁶¹ On the importance of a human rights-compliant and non-discriminatory approach in the implementation of the European Green Deal, see Equinet, *Preliminary assessment of the EU Green Deal's impact on equality: Survey of current practices and needs of European Equality Bodies* (2023); and European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights (FRA), *Towards a fundamental rights-compliant European Green Deal* (2025).

There are, in any case, instances of actual **use of HRJs**, but mainly by States and primarily in front of the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) rather than the CJEU. An exception is the CJEU case *Ville de Paris and Others v. Federal Republic of Germany and Others*,⁶² where the defendant States (Germany and Hungary) referred to the free movement of goods and the right to property as HRJs for possible restrictions on the powers of the applicant municipalities to limit the circulation of vehicles in the context of air pollution abatement measures. Nevertheless, in the litigation context, the distinction between HRJs and the traditional balancing of rights can be difficult to make.⁶³

Another characteristic of the use of HRJs in climate litigation, which is especially pronounced in investment- and trade-related litigation⁶⁴ but can also be found in front of the ECtHR and CJEU, is recourse not to HRJs as such but to arguments based on **related notions** (on which see above in this section).

As reported in another contribution for the Project, courts have often left and will likely continue to leave a wide **margin of appreciation** to governments (and the EU) in the development and implementation of their climate action, thus allowing for HRJs and related notions laid out in rather general terms.⁶⁵ Nonetheless, it cannot be excluded that, as the impacts of climate change become more destructive and governments continue to not implement adequate responses, courts might interpret their role differently and limit the discretion allowed to governments.⁶⁶

The fact remains that, at present, **access** to the CJEU by individuals and NGOs is limited by the restrictive approach adopted by the Court with respect to these actors' legal standing (namely, the so-called *Plaumann* test applied to Article 263(4) TFEU), so that human rights-based arguments in the context of climate-related proceedings are not likely to arise often. Indeed, the most well-known cases premised on the CFREU – *Carvalho and Others* (C-565/19 P) and *Sabo and Others* (C-297/20 P) – failed precisely on such a basis. This has to date resulted, among others, in substantial obstacles to access to the CJEU both by **individuals living in third countries** and affected by the EU27 insufficient climate action (such as individuals from Fiji and Kenya practising herding, farming, fishing and eco-tourism, who

⁶² Joined Cases C-177/19 P to C-179/19 P *Ville de Paris and Others v. Federal Republic of Germany and Others*, ECLI:EU:C:2022:10.

⁶³ Maria Nääv, *The Doctrinal Void – Human Rights Justifications and Positive Obligations under the European Convention of Human Rights* (forthcoming).

⁶⁴ Investment- and trade-related litigation, which can also involve the EU, has been analysed in greater detail for Deliverable D7.6.

⁶⁵ Chiara Tea Antoniazzi, *Report on Climate-Related Litigation and the Separation of Powers* (last updated January 2026).

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

were applicants in the *Carvalho* case) and by **indigenous peoples**, living in and outside EU Member States (such as the Sami people, who were applicants in the same case through an association representing young Samis and whose traditional occupations in reindeer husbandry stand to be seriously affected by climate change). Nevertheless, human rights-based cases might find alternative ways to reach the Court, including through preliminary references.

4.3.3 *The Relationship Between the Internal and External Dimensions of EU Climate Policy*

While generally speaking the external competence of the EU on a certain subject matter follows its internal one (the so-called principle of parallelism of internal and external competences⁶⁷), **the connection between the external and internal dimensions is particularly strong** in the area of climate change, from both a legal and a political perspective. Indeed, a) climate policy is inherently aimed at having an external dimension or impact, if the policy is to have any effectiveness; and b) the EU leadership in the climate change area at a global level has primarily consisted of a leadership by example: as a consequence, ensuring consistency between the two dimensions is crucial for the EU credibility on the international stage.⁶⁸

The pronounced and wide-ranging external dimension of EU policy and actions in this area (or, in other words, the role of the EU as a global actor) emerges clearly from both the main legislative acts and the relevant litigation examined above. Nevertheless, as made explicit by the European Green Deal, EU institutions generally interpret the external dimension of EU climate policy as referring primarily to diplomacy, trade and development aid.⁶⁹ On their part,

⁶⁷ The principle of parallelism originates in the Opinion 1/76 by the CJEU (Opinion 1/76 – *Laying-up fund for inland waterway vessels* [1977] ECR 741). In para 4 of that opinion the CJEU noted as follows: “Although the internal Community measures are only adopted when the international agreement is concluded and made enforceable, ... the power to bind the Community vis-à-vis third countries nevertheless flows by implication from the provisions of the Treaty creating the internal power and in so far as the participation of the Community in the international agreement is ... necessary for the attainment of that one of the objectives of the Community”. However, it should be noted that the adoption of an internal act of legislation by the Union is not necessary for the existence of external competences of the EU. See e.g. Case C-459/03, *Mox Plant* [2006] ECR I-4635, in which the CJEU noted as follows: “the existence of the Community’s external competence in regard to protection of the marine environment is not, in principle, contingent on the adoption of measures of secondary law covering the area in question ...”.

⁶⁸ Rüdiger K. W. Wurzel, James Connelly & Duncan Liefferink (eds.), *THE EUROPEAN UNION IN INTERNATIONAL CLIMATE CHANGE POLITICS: STILL TAKING A LEAD?* (2017); Sebastian Oberthür & Marc Pallemerts, *The EU’s Internal and External Climate Policies: An Historical Overview*, in Sebastian Oberthür & Marc Pallemerts (eds.), *THE NEW CLIMATE POLICIES OF THE EUROPEAN UNION: INTERNAL LEGISLATION AND CLIMATE DIPLOMACY* (2010) 27; Eva Pander Maat, *Leading by Example, Ideas or Coercion? The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism as a Case of Hybrid EU Climate Leadership*, 7 *EUROPEAN PAPERS – EUROPEAN FORUM* 55 (2022), <<https://www.europeanpapers.eu/europeanforum/leading-by-example-ideas-coercion-carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism>> accessed 26 January 2026.

⁶⁹ See above sub-section i.

scholars have mostly scrutinised the compatibility of EU climate measures with EU and Member States' international obligations pertaining to the international climate change regime, membership in the World Trade Organization and customary norms on State jurisdiction.⁷⁰

What appears to be frequently missing – in the adoption of legislation or in defences before courts, as well as in the academic literature – is adequate consideration of the existence and extent of **EU extraterritorial human rights obligations** in the area of climate change. Indeed, the EU climate policy – or the lack of sufficient climate action on the part of the EU – can negatively affect the rights of individuals and communities living in third countries. The question therefore arises whether the EU has any obligation to respect, protect and/or fulfil the rights of these persons when taking climate action or omitting to take climate action. While in the area of migration the debate about the existence of extraterritorial obligations can rely on some reference points (although the situation is in constant evolution as new externalisation policies emerge, see above section 4.2), the diffuse nature of both causes and effects of climate change have made matters particularly complicated. Tentative answers to questions about the existence and extent of extraterritorial human rights obligations of the EU specifically in the area of climate change have been provided in an open-access article published in the context of the HRJust Project, which takes into consideration existing obstacles but also some **special features of the EU legal framework** that make it particularly open – at least potentially – to the recognition of extraterritorial human rights obligations.⁷¹

The fact remains that, at present, most EU climate-related acts focus exclusively on the rights and interests of EU citizens, notwithstanding the acts' significant external dimension, the impact of the EU climate (in)action (as the EU27 remains among the top GHG emitters), and the proclaimed global leadership of the EU in climate mitigation and adaptation. The Deforestation Regulation represents an exception in this respect, insofar as it clearly and rather extensively addresses the human rights of people living outside the EU, such as indigenous peoples, local communities and smallholder producers. In the context of litigation, legal proceedings before the CJEU both premised on human rights arguments and related to the external dimension of the EU climate policy have to date been rejected as inadmissible because

⁷⁰ See, among others, Dobson, fn 58; Bednarek, fn 60; Lorand Bartels, *The WTO Legality of the Application of the EU's Emission Trading System to Aviation*, 23 EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW 429 (2012); Joanne Scott & Lavanya Rajamani, *EU Climate Change Unilateralism*, 23 EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INTERNATIONAL LAW 469 (2012); Christina Voigt, *Up in the Air: Aviation, the EU Emissions Trading Scheme and the Question of Jurisdiction*, 14 CAMBRIDGE YEARBOOK OF EUROPEAN LEGAL STUDIES 475 (2012); and Ilaria Espa, Joseph Francois & Harro van Asselt, *The EU Proposal for a Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM): An Analysis under WTO and Climate Change Law*, WTI working paper 06-2022.

⁷¹ Chiara Tea Antoniazzi, *Extraterritorial Human Rights Obligations in the Area of Climate Change: Why the European Union Should Take Them Seriously*, 9 EUROPEAN PAPERS 479 (2024).

of the lack of legal standing of the applicants,⁷² in accordance with the above-mentioned restrictive interpretation of Article 263(4) TFEU by the CJEU.

Nevertheless, in light of ongoing developments within climate-related litigation, failing to consider the extraterritorial human rights obligations of EU institutions in the conception and implementation of their climate policy puts them at risk of breaching international and EU treaties' norms. Politically, lack of sufficient consideration of the human rights impact of the EU climate (in)action outside the EU27's territory endangers the global leadership of the EU in the areas of both climate action and the protection of human rights; risks antagonising developing countries that are more vulnerable to the effects of climate change and their civil societies; and exposes the EU to accusations of double standards, if only the human rights or well-being of individuals living in the EU27's territory are considered.

4.4 The EU and Covid: Competences and HRJs

The Covid-19 pandemic posed serious cross-broader health threats, as well as having the potential to disrupt all areas of human activity (work, travel, education, economics, politics, etc.). As discussed in more detail in Deliverable 4.1, the Covid 19 pandemic had a wide-ranging impact on human rights – either directly or indirectly e.g. through a 'chilling effect' resulting from a first order intrusion into e.g. a freedom of movement that also affected the enjoyment or exercise of other human rights of the individuals. Without the intention to be exhaustive, the following human rights can be mentioned: freedom of movement; freedom of association and assembly, including freedom of expression and electoral and participatory rights; freedom of thought, conscience and religion; the right not to be discriminated against; the right to liberty and security of the persons; educational rights; the rights of the child, the elderly and persons with disabilities; the right to work and the freedom to engage in commercial activity; and social rights.

While the foregoing human rights affected by the Covid 19 pandemic tend not to be so-called 'absolute' rights, i.e. human rights that would allow for no restrictions, nor be subject to derogation during a state of emergency threatening the life of the nation, the Covid 19 pandemic did also affect, unfortunately, the right to life which is an absolute, non-derogable human right.

⁷² See the proceedings mentioned in the section above, namely Case C-565/19 P, *Carvalho and Others v Parliament and Council*, ECLI:EU:C:2021:252; and Case C-297/20 P, *Sabo and Others v Parliament and Council*, ECLI:EU:C:2021:24.

More generally, the Covid-19 pandemic also exposed a far-reaching threat to the health of the population across Europe and the world.

Hence, a standard justification of governments for various Covid 19 pandemic measures often was that these measures were justified for the purpose of protecting the health of the population and, ultimately, the right to life of the individuals (see in more detail Deliverable 4.1 of HRJs in Finland, Sweden and Taiwan during the Covid 19 pandemic). At the same time, however, these measures entailed restrictions on those numerous other human rights mentioned above. As states have a positive obligation to act to protect the health of the population and, ultimately, the right to life of the individuals, governments' actions and measures counteracting the Covid 19 pandemic, which at the same time often limited other human rights mentioned above, brought up tensions and even conflicts between states' positive and negative obligations in relation to human rights (for conflicts of negative and positive obligations, see in more detailed in Deliverable 3.2, presenting a completed theory of States' HRJs, addressing legitimacy, transparency and State accountability, including typology and evaluation of human rights justifications).

As with climate change, dealing with such cross-border health threats as those posed by Covid-19 effectively and robustly inevitably requires effective coordinated action at the European Union (EU) level in addition to various actions taken at the national, regional or local level. In addition, effective counteraction to pandemics like Covid-19 requires cooperation with international partners such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) at their apex in alignment with the EU's and its Member States external and internal actions.

However, the competences of the EU remain quite limited in the area of public health. Only the common safety concerns in public health matters defined in Article 168 (4) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) are included in the field of *shared competences* pursuant to Article 4 of the TFEU. Within the field of shared competences, the EU and its Member States are able to legislate and adopt legally binding acts. Member States exercise their own competence where the EU does not exercise, or has decided not to exercise, its own competence.

The aspects pertaining to common safety concerns and, accordingly, falling within the field of shared competences are prescribed in Article 168(4) of the TFEU as follows:

“(a) measures setting high standards of quality and safety of organs and substances of human origin, blood and blood derivatives; these measures shall not prevent any Member State [MOU1] from maintaining or introducing more stringent protective measures;

(b) measures in the veterinary and phytosanitary fields which have as their direct objective the protection of public health;

(c) measures setting high standards of quality and safety for medicinal products and devices for medical use.”

In addition, Article 168(5) of the TFEU provides that “The European Parliament and the Council, acting in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure and after consulting the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, may also adopt incentive measures designed to protect and improve human health and in particular to combat the major cross-border health scourges, measures concerning monitoring, early warning of and combating serious cross-border threats to health, and measures which have as their direct objective the protection of public health regarding tobacco and the abuse of alcohol, excluding any harmonisation of the laws and regulations of the Member States.” Hence, Article 168 (5) of the TFEU can be seen as providing a legal basis for EU actions against COVID-19 to the extent that combatting “major cross-border health scourges” and “serious cross-border threats to health” is concerned.

Article 168(2) of the TFEU also entrusts the Commission with the task to support the coordination of Member States’ actions in the field of public health as follows: “Member States shall, in liaison with the Commission, coordinate among themselves their policies and programmes in the areas referred to in paragraph 1. The Commission may, in close contact with the Member States, take any useful initiative to promote such coordination, in particular initiatives aiming at the establishment of guidelines and indicators, the organisation of exchange of best practice, and the preparation of the necessary elements for periodic monitoring and evaluation. The European Parliament shall be kept fully informed.” Thus, while the Commission is given a supportive/coordination role concerning Member States’ voluntary cooperation and actions, this seems to exclude the possibility to adopt legally binding instruments.

The exceptional circumstances of the Covid 19 pandemic encouraged the EU institutions to rely on broader treaty mechanisms in order to facilitate coordinated action beyond the ordinary limits of EU public health competences. In particular, the vaccine procurement strategy

demonstrated how the Union used existing legal flexibility to expand its coordinating role during the crisis. Although public health largely remains within the competence of the Member States, the European Commission negotiated advance purchase agreements with pharmaceutical companies on behalf of all Member States through a centralized procurement system. This approach was justified by reference to the need to ensure equal access to vaccines, avoid internal competition between Member States, and strengthen the collective bargaining position of the EU vis à vis global pharmaceutical producers.⁷³ The arrangement reflected the logic underlying Article 122 TFEU and the broader flexibility mechanisms available under the treaties, which permit Union action where this is necessary to attain treaty objectives in exceptional circumstances. The gradual expansion of EU action in the health field through crisis driven initiatives has also been described as part of the emerging European Health Union.⁷⁴

The vaccine procurement strategy showed the EU's role as a regional actor during the pandemic. By centralising negotiations and coordinating vaccine distribution across the Union, the EU assumed functions that traditionally belonged to the national level. This strengthened the perception that the EU is capable of exercising collective crisis management and mobilising resources and coordinating responses across borders.⁷⁵ At the same time, the procurement strategy had an important external dimension because it enabled the EU to act collectively in global vaccine markets and to engage internationally as a single negotiating actor. In this sense, the pandemic accelerated the development of a more visible regional role for the EU in public health governance, even though the formal distribution of competences under the treaties remained largely unchanged.⁷⁶

Finally, Article 168(3) of the TFEU provides that “the Union and the Member States shall foster cooperation with third countries and the competent international organisations in the sphere of public health.” However, while this provision provides for the competence of the EU and its Member States to “foster cooperation” with third countries and international

⁷³ R. Beetsma and F. Nicoli, “On the Design of a European Health Union: Public Preferences, Trust, and Experience With the Covid 19 Crisis,” 2025, *Regulation and Governance*.

⁷⁴ M. McKee and A. de Ruijter, “The Path to a European Health Union,” 2024, *The Lancet Regional Health Europe*.

⁷⁵ I. Kickbusch and A. de Ruijter, “How a European Health Union Can Strengthen Global Health,” 2021, *The Lancet Regional Health Europe*.

⁷⁶ A. Bojar and H. Kriesi, “Policymaking in the EU Under Crisis Conditions: Covid and Refugee Crises Compared,” 2023, *Comparative European Politics*.

organisations, the scope of such cooperation is reduced due to the limited competences of the EU in public health matters. This also means that “geopolitics” could only play a role in the EU’s strategy, resources and reach during Covid-19 pandemic within the limits of the powers conferred upon the EU by the founding treaties and of the objectives assigned to it therein. The “external role” of the EU during Covid-19 is discussed more below.

Otherwise, public health remains an area in which the EU retains only *supporting competences* in accordance with Article 6 of the TFEU. Within the field of supporting competences, the EU can only intervene to support, coordinate or complement the action of its Member States. Legally binding EU acts must not require the harmonisation of the laws or regulations of the Member States.

According to Article 168(3) of the TFEU, “the Union and the Member States shall foster cooperation with third countries and the competent international organisations in the sphere of public health.” Also, given the principle of parallelism between the EU’s internal and external competencies, it follows that the EU’s external role was essentially similar to its internal role during Covid-19. Thus, the EU, notably the European Commission, mainly assumed externally (globally) a supportive/coordination role of cooperation and actions which were based on legally non-binding soft law type of measures instead of entering into agreements with third countries or undertaking other legally binding instruments. For instance, the EU institutions issued a joint communication on the Global EU response to COVID-19 for the purpose of fostering international cooperation and global action.⁷⁷ However, while the EU thus showed global solidarity by supporting international cooperation and multilateral solutions, the main objective of the EU action was still *internal*, and essentially designed to combat the coronavirus crisis within the European Union through the coordination of a common EU-wide response to the Covid-19 pandemic.

5. Main policy recommendations

One can emerge from the maze of foregoing considerations of the EU internal and external human rights regimes, EU competences and human rights justifications by the EU in the fields

⁷⁷ JOINT COMMUNICATION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT, THE COUNCIL, THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL COMMITTEE AND THE COMMITTEE OF THE REGIONS, Communication on the Global EU response to COVID-19, JOIN(2020) 11 final.

of Migration, Climate and Covid, including reflections of global megatrends and challenges shaping global landscape of human rights, with the following set of more general/cross-cutting policy recommendations, supplemented by a number of more thematic policy recommendations on covid, migration and climate change.

Since this Deliverable 7.7 is partly based on Deliverable 2.2 (Recommendations on policy, legislation and regulations, EU role and addressing gaps in regulations and individual human rights protection as effects of States' HRJ); Deliverable 3.2 (Typology and Evaluation of Human Rights Justifications); Deliverable 7.5 (Inclusive Democracy, reflecting gender and intersectionality); and Deliverable 7.6 (Overview of States' practice of HRJs, including findings in three thematic WPs), as well as the deliverables representing background research towards this deliverable 7.7 as described above, the following main policy recommendations also largely, if not exclusively, complement and renew the policy recommendations made in these deliverables.

I General/cross-cutting policy recommendations

- **Upholding human rights in the development of new EU laws, actions and policies both internally and externally.** As discussed in more detail in the report, “A Normative Core for a Geopolitical Europe: Policy Recommendation on Human Rights in European Union External Action” by Sari Kouvo, human rights are one of the fundamental values upon which the European Union is built alongside the rule of law and democracy. In an increasingly turbulent and unpredictable geopolitical landscape, it is more important than ever that the EU remains a steadfast defender and promoter of human rights (and the rule of law and democracy since they are closely interlinked with human rights). The protection of human rights cannot be a secondary concern in the face of global instability. It is absolutely vital that the EU maintain a focus on the protection and promotion of fundamental and human rights both externally and internally. With the confusion concerning the US essentially withdrawing from or discounting the current rule-based order on the international level, particularly concerning human rights, it becomes even more important that the EU stands fast and possibly deepens its focus on human rights at the international level and its foreign policy towards specific countries. This is a necessity particularly where democracy is at least part of a country's self-image. This helps to empower civil society to support

the development and deepening of human rights as well as their capacity to challenge human rights justifications in such countries. Withdrawing support to human rights at an international level also risks European civil society's understanding of the value of human rights at the EU member state level.

- **Recognising the special importance of human rights in the EU's external relations.**

While it is important to focus on the protection of fundamental and human rights in the EU, human rights should be of supreme significance in the EU's external relations. A reference is here also made to the above-mentioned report by Sari Kouvo on the normative Core for a geopolitical Europe and making policy recommendations as regards human rights in EU external action. Particularly concerning countries such as Taiwan, where there is an expressed political intent to maintain and implement human rights, EU external policy in support of human rights provides a tool for civil society organisations (CSOs) to advocate for human rights implementation and counteract human rights justifications by the Taiwan government, both in the legislative process as well as in the courts.

- More generally, concerning the EU's external policy and human rights, the EEAS should focus on the development of 1) access to justice and 2) empowerment of civil society organisations. Access to justice or its absence is a key to actual implementation of human rights, both within the EU internally as well externally. Another related issue is empowerment in regard to CSO advocacy in terms of both legislation and litigation. Again this is a necessity to shoring up democracy, whether at the Member State level or in terms of EU external policy.
- EU external policy should also provide support to ensuring that human rights/fundamental rights are an essential part of higher education. This is particularly important so that CSOs develop the necessary tools for challenging human rights justifications currently being asserted by national governments. All too often, their expertise is limited which means that as government experts use the rhetoric of human rights, such experts can confuse the issues making it difficult for e.g. CSOs to adequately address the weaknesses in such rhetoric.

- **Ensuring consistency in the EU actions in the field of human rights both externally and internally.** For a long time one major problem has been the discrepancy between the internal and external EU human rights regimes, which has resulted in the so-called

double standards phenomenon. Double standards should be avoided, and sufficient consistency ought to be achieved to preserve the authority and credibility of the EU laws, actions and policies both externally and internally, including the very functioning of the European integration project, based as it is on trust and mutual recognition.

- **Monitoring the use of human rights justifications (and “related notions”) by Member States and carefully considering their own use of human rights justifications within their competences.** To this end, EU institutions could avail themselves of the expertise of the EU Agency for Fundamental Rights and its unique position as a forum for cooperation with both CSOs and National Human Rights Institutions of Member States. CSOs in particular can play a crucial role in holding States and EU institutions accountable.
- **Supporting the role and diversity of civil society, including human rights defenders; supporting current and new patterns of civil society engagement.** Civil society is a key to exposing and challenging HRJs by governments in a wide range of situations, including the drafting of legislation and adoption of new policies and actions, as well as when bringing human rights challenges in the courts and other forums concerning the exercising of government or other forms of public power.
- **Applying a holistic approach.** Due to the complexity of the combined effect of the above-discussed megatrends and challenges at the international level that are likely to shape the environment for human rights in coming years, there is a need for a holistic human rights approach to addressing the combined effect of the various megatrends and challenges e.g. in the fields of migration, climate change and covid. This is even more so since migration, climate change and covid are interlinked and complementary in many ways as the following thematic policy recommendations will also display.

II Thematic policy recommendations on covid, migration and climate change

Policy recommendations in the area of migration

- Focus on groups of migrants which are at particular risk, such as unaccompanied children, children with their families, people with disabilities and ethnic minority groups, as both voluntary migration and asylum is likely to increase due to the trends

listed above. In particular it is important that a clearer gender-responsive approach to migration governance is utilised in internal and external EU policies.

Policy recommendations in the area of climate change

- **Counteracting climate change and environmental degradation is needed in order to respect, protect and fulfil the human rights of present and future generations,** which are and will increasingly be threatened by the impacts of climate change. Human rights considerations should be fully incorporated in the conception and implementation of EU climate policy. There should also be adequate consideration paid to the existence and extent of EU extraterritorial human rights obligations in the field of climate change, as these are currently being re-shaped by courts and as the EU legal order is in itself rather open to the recognition of human rights obligations towards individuals and groups living in third countries.
- **Striving to integrate EU global leadership in the fight against climate change and its global leadership in the promotion of human rights.** Applying a human rights-based approach to climate action would strengthen its credibility on the international stage and its relations with those countries whose populations are most affected by climate change, while also empowering civil society more generally. At the same time, the EU should be aware of the impacts that any perceived inconsistency between their internal and external policies can have on the behaviour of third States and other relevant actors in the area of climate change. Accordingly, the utmost attention should be devoted to avoiding situations where the EU can be accused of applying double standards.
- **Recognising the importance of climate action in its interactions with other sectors.** Counteracting effectively climate change and environmental degradation is one of the main means to prevent the emergence of pandemics such as COVID-19, including all the problems related to human rights and democracy that pandemics and other health crises can give rise to. From another perspective, climate change is bound to have an increasing impact on movements of people, including transnational ones, which will generate new protection needs.

Policy recommendations in the area of COVID-19

- **Rights-based approach to the management of pandemics.** The Covid-19 pandemic had a wide-ranging impact on human rights. While governments across the world took

urgent measures, even emergency measures, to counter Covid 19 for the purpose of safeguarding the human right of health and, ultimately, everyone's right to life, these measures simultaneously impacted a whole range of other fundamental and human rights to an extent rarely experienced in peacetime, including freedom of movement, freedom of religion, the right of non-discrimination, freedom of association, freedom of assembly, right to education, the right to engage in work and freedom to conduct a business. Covid 19 had an especially negative impact on women, children and young people in situations of vulnerability, people with disabilities, older people, Roma, migrants, and people in precarious working conditions. Most fundamental and human rights affected by Covid 19 were not so-called absolute rights allowing for no restrictions or not being subject to derogation during a state of emergency, threatening the life of the nation. However, one of the main lessons of the Covid 19 pandemic is the importance of rights-based management of pandemics for the purpose of ensuring that all limitations to fundamental and human rights are consistent with legal safeguards and that their impact on particular groups is adequately taken into account. Hence, while restrictions may be permissible within human rights law itself, due attention must nonetheless be given that any pandemic measure restricting fundamental and human rights is assessed, case-by-case, for its permissibility. In practice, this means that each measure for countering future pandemics must be assessed through the permissible limitations test, reflected in e.g. Article 52.1 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and Articles 8-11 of the ECHR. In short, since the EU is founded on the respect for human rights (and the rule of law and democracy), counter-pandemic measures must be pursued in accordance with the rule of law and subject to fundamental and human rights obligations.

- **Co-operation with international partners with the World Health Organisation (WHO) at their apex.** Effective and robust response to health crises like the Covid-19 pandemic requires not only collective cross-border actions by the EU in addition to various national, regional and local efforts. In addition, multifaceted cooperation with international partners with World Health Organisation (WHO) at their apex in alignment with the EU's and its Member States external and internal actions is needed for the purpose of assisting EU Member States and third countries to counteract the pandemics like Covid-19 effectively.

